

ON THE ISSUE OF METHODOLOGICAL, GEODETIC AND PRACTICAL SUPPORT FOR THE RATIONAL USE OF AGRICULTURAL LAND

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Abstract

The article reveals the methodological foundations of organising land use on the basis of sustainable development. The issues of geodetic and practical support for the formation of a balanced land use of agricultural formations and their interconnection in solving problems of land use and protection have been highlighted. The use of land by existing land-owners and land users has been analysed the directions for further use and protection of land for a long period of time have been provided.

It has been mentioned that in order to improve the system of rational land use on the basis of sustainable development, it is necessary to develop an ecological and economic mechanism to stimulate the implementation of measures for the protection, reproduction and conservation of ecosystem functions of land resources, as well as methodological, geodetic and practical support.

Keywords: Land management project, topographic and geodetic works, rational land use, technological groups of land, land organisation, crop rotation, territory improvement, environmental and economic justification of the project.

Statement of the problem. The issue of methodological, geodetic and practical support for the organisation of rational land use is relevant today, as it concerns primarily the environmentally friendly use of land resources, ecological protection of the environment, increasing fertility and soil protection.

The relevance of the study is determined by the Land Code of Ukraine [1], the Laws of Ukraine "On Land Management" [4], "On Topographic, Geodetic and Cartographic Activities" [5] and other regulatory legal acts, with the aim of developing land relations, improving the efficiency of control over the rational use and protection of land, which play a leading role in the economic development of our country and therefore attract the greatest attention. This study will allow to take into account the specific conditions of the administrative-territorial entity and its soil and climatic resources and, on this basis, to determine a set of balanced measures for the use and protection of land, improvement of soil fertility, formation of environmentally safe agricultural landscapes, as well as their methodological, geodetic and practical support.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The category of sustainable land use is reflected in the Law of Ukraine "On Land Management", which defines sustainable land use as a form and corresponding methods of land use that ensure optimal parameters of the ecological and socio-economic functions of the territory [4].

When developing a land management project, a set of geodetic works and desk-based processing of the results is carried out. The complex of works includes: preparatory

topographic and geodetic works, cartographic and land management works, desk work, preparation and execution of technical land management documentation, as well as establishing the boundaries of the land plot in kind (on the ground) and fixing them with boundary markers [2].

Preparatory work includes the collection and analysis of available land management documentation, land inventory materials, planning and cartographic materials, legal grounds for granting land ownership (use), information on the existence of disputed issues regarding the boundaries of the land plot, a list of restrictions on the use of the land plot and existing land easements, and lists of coordinates of points of the state geodetic network.

Chamber works are carried out to process data obtained as a result of topographic and geodetic works, land management works and preparation of technical documentation on land management to establish the boundaries of a land plot in kind (on the ground) [3].

Therefore, well-grounded methodological, geodetic, scientific and practical developments are needed to improve the system of agricultural land tenure and land use, increase soil fertility, and regulate the use of each plot, since the further development of agricultural formation and the welfare of residents depend on the intensity of use.

Objective of the study is to highlight the issues of methodological, geodetic and practical support that should be addressed in the development of land management projects for the ecological and economic improvement of land use in agricultural formations.

Research methodology. The methodological basis of the research is general scientific methods of knowledge: historical, dialectical, empirical, systemic, formal-logical, structural-functional, comprehensive, technical-legal, statistical, cartographic.

The main results of the study. The study of methodological, geodetic and practical support for the rational use and protection of land within the Ternivka rural united territorial community of Cherkasy district, Cherkasy region, was carried out on the example of the land of LLC "Avangard".

The following topographic and geodetic materials were used in the development of the land management project:

- a land management project for the organisation of land shares for members of the Peremoha CAE of the Ternivka village council of Smila district;
- project for the formation of the territory of Ternivka village council;
- project of establishing the boundaries of settlements of Ternivka village council;
- project of on-farm land management of the Peremoha farm of the Ternivka village council of Smila district;
- technical report on the correction of soil survey materials;
- technical report on the correction of planning and cartographic materials of previous years' surveys.

Agricultural land within the Ternivka rural united territorial community covers 2490.8501 hectares, which is 89.43% of the total area:

- LLC "Avangard" - 1082.4884 hectares;
- Berezniaky Agricultural Complex - 945.0700 hectares;

- Citizens who have been granted land for ownership and use - 393.7567 ha;

- reserve land and land not granted for ownership and permanent use within settlements (not granted for temporary use) - 69.5350 hectares.

Non-agricultural lands are divided into the following categories by their main designated purpose and comprise:

- Residential and public development land - 132,4253 ha - (5.41%);
- forestry land - 3,9000 ha - (0.16%);
- water fund land - 77,2200 ha - (3.15%);
- land for industry, transport, communications, energy, defence and other purposes - 45,4247 hectares (1.85%).

The land plots located within the boundaries of the Ternivka rural united territorial community belong to the Forest-Steppe zone of Ukraine. According to the Smila weather station, 595 mm of precipitation falls per year, including 381 mm during the growing season (April - October). The average long-term temperature for the year is +7,4⁰C. The average monthly temperature of the hottest month of July is +19,2⁰C. In general, the growing season lasts 205 days, and the period of active vegetation (temperature above +10⁰C) lasts 160-165 days.

The relief of the project area is closely related to the geological structure. The predominant terrain type here is watershed poorly and well-drained loess plains, with valley-sandstone terrain types along river valleys, and in some places, moraine-sandstone and moraine plains.

Tables 1 and 2 present the relief characteristics of the fields of crop rotations of LLC "Avangard" located on the territory of Ternivka rural united territorial community in the context of the two proposed crop rotations.

Table 1.

Distribution of arable land by slope steepness in terms of crop rotation fields on the territory of LLC "Avangard" (field crop rotation)

№ fields	Area, ha	The steepness of the slopes				
		0-1°	1-2°	2-3°	3-5°	7-10°
I	115,9809	96,6047	18,2185	1,1577	-	-
II	123,6168	68,0598	48,5759	6,9811	-	-
III	101,4655	75,1163	24,3968	1,9524	-	-
IV	108,9428	87,0756	10,9721	10,8951	-	-
V	131,1257	79,3912	51,7345		-	-
VI	127,9147	98,5300	28,1833	1,2014	-	-
VII	104,6142	60,7519	39,9587	3,9036	-	-
Всього	813,6606	565,5295	222,0398	26,0913	-	-

Table 2.

Distribution of arable land by slope steepness in the context of crop rotation fields on the territory of LLC "Avangard" (fodder crop rotation)

№ fields	Area, ha	The steepness of the slopes				
		0-1°	1-2°	2-3°	3-5°	7-10°
I	39,5783	35,1527	3,7453	0,6803	-	-
II	44,5410	39,2217	3,4027	1,9166	-	-
III	47,2308	43,1303	4,1005	-	-	-
IV	39,1452	28,4592	8,9639	1,7221	-	-
V	40,9802	17,0562	5,5310	6,3656	11,0118	1,0156
VI	40,1481	38,0206	2,1275			
Total	251,6236	201,0407	227,8709	10,6846	11,0118	1,0156

The soil cover of the farm is mainly represented by typical and podzolised black soils on the wide watershed plateaus, by eroded soils on the sloping lands, and by meadow glacial and meadow-boggy soils on the lowlands.

The land plots of LLC “Avangard” are located at different distances from settlements, farms and road networks and are mainly represented by grey, dark grey podzolised soils and typical light and medium loamy black soils, respectively.

The weighted average distance from arable land to farmyards is three to five kilometres. Up to 20% of the arable land is adjacent to paved roads, and the rest is served by dirt roads.

The fields of the proposed crop rotations have size deviations within the permissible limits to the average field size. The soil cover of the fields of the designed crop rotations mainly meets the requirements for growing the accepted set of crops. All fields are designed to take maximum account of the relief and provide for tillage and sowing of crops across the slope on eroded soils. The structure of the sown areas of the land leased by “Avangard” is based on scientifically proven crop rotation schemes.

The principle of environmental and economic feasibility, maximum use of soil and climatic factors, which is the main, cheapest and most environmentally friendly means of increasing the bioproductive potential of all lands, including the land leased by LLC “Avangard”, is the basis for determining the optimal structure of sown areas when developing a land management project.

Taking into account the indicators of soil quality and land suitability for growing major crops, the land management project envisages field and fodder crop rotation on the land plots of “Avangard”.

The following crop rotation is envisaged:

1. Winter cereals (wheat);
2. Corn;
3. Soybeans;
4. Winter cereals (wheat);
5. Soybeans.

The crop rotation plan is in line with the land transformation plans, which envisage reducing the timeframe for bringing the land under cultivation and using it for crops. Particular attention is paid to increasing grain production, as well as creating seed stocks and providing livestock with nutritious feed.

The proposed land management project ensures an ecologically balanced soil and water management of the territory based on the study and in-depth analysis of soil conditions, relief, vegetation cover, the degree of

land suitability for growing crops, erosion hazards and environmental load of the territory.

Conclusions. The issues of rational land use have always been relevant. But today, the most important problem is to ensure sustainable development of land use, the essence of which is to achieve a harmonious balance between population, consumption and the ability of the land to support life.

The article presents the ecological and economic justification of land management, methodological, geodetic and practical support for land management projects. It analyses the use of land by landowners and land users and provides directions for further use and protection of land for a long period of time.

In order to improve the system of rational land use on the basis of sustainable development, it is necessary to develop an environmental and economic mechanism to stimulate the implementation of measures for the protection, restoration and conservation of the ecosystem functions of land resources, as well as methodological, geodetic and practical support for them.

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